

Characterization of touch perception on the torso

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Abstract. Much research has been carried out into touch on the hands and haptic interactions. However, the skin over the body contributes to our sense of self and interactions we have with the world. We aim to investigate somatosensory perception on the human torso, focusing on the breast, and comparing this to the forearm and glabrous hand skin. The goal is to better understand the fundamental mechanisms in somatosensory perception, to apply the insights to reproduce realistic sensations in breast prosthetics, after mastectomy. We investigate affective touch (pleasantness) and discriminative touch (force detection), as well as thermal perception thresholds, over these skin sites. We present here the context of the study, the methodology and some expected results. We aim to relate these findings to the underlying neurophysiology of the skin and identify how somatosensation can be highly dependent on the body area stimulated, requiring a consideration of this throughout all prosthetic and haptic devices.

Keywords: Breast sensation, Temperature perception, Tactile perception.

1 Introduction

Although many studies have investigated touch and haptic interactions using the hands, far fewer have looked at touch over the human body. We use our hands throughout our daily lives, yet the signals from the whole of our body are required to know our place in space and how to interact with it. There is a need to investigate fundamental functioning of skin over the body, to apply this in clinical contexts, such as prosthetics. Hand and leg prosthetics have evolved greatly over recent years and have started to incorporate tactile feedback to embody the prosthetic, such as through nerve stimulation [1]. In a collaborative project [2], we aim to better understand breast sensation, to apply this in regaining sensations after mastectomy. A few studies have investigated touch acuity over the body, but very little is known about somatosensation on the torso. We aim to investigate different aspects of somatosensation on the breast and compare this with control sites, namely on just below the breast, the forearm, and the glabrous skin of the hand. We will use measures of affective touch, via the pleasantness of a brush stroke, discriminative touch, via the detection of calibrated monofilaments, and thermal detection thresholds of warm and cool. Of the few studies on the torso and breast, affective touch on the stomach was found to be lower than other areas [3], breast tactile acuity is generally lower [4, 5], and thermal warm sensations can differ over the

breast and torso [6]. We aim to investigate these processes more thoroughly and compare them with sensations from the glabrous hand and forearm, to investigate affective and discriminative tactile sensations, as well as thermal perception thresholds.

2 Method

We are recruiting healthy women and men to participate, where we collect supplementary information including age, breasts and torso size, history of breastfeeding and if they are taking hormonal contraception, as well as responses to a touch experiences and attitudes questionnaire (TEAQ short version <https://osf.io/qg5he>). The study is divided in two experiments, where we test selected body sites, namely the nipple-areola complex, the upper breast skin, the torso skin below the breast, the forearm, and the glabrous skin of the hand (Fig. 1B). For both experiments, we collect warm and cool perception thresholds using thermode (QSTlab) over all sites. In the first set of experiments, we use a standard brush stroking approach to investigate affective touch, delivered by a Rotary Tactile Stimulator (RTS, Dancer Design; Fig. 1A, C) using a controlled force (0.4 N) at five velocities (0.3, 1, 3, 10, 30 cm/s) over the body sites. The velocities are randomly tested at each skin site and skin sites are tested in a block-randomized order. Each velocity is repeated three times and after each brush stroke, the participant rates the pleasantness (unpleasant-pleasant) and intensity (very weak-very intense) perception on a visual analog scale. In the second set of experiments, we use a brush stroke applied manually at three randomized velocities (0.3, 3, 30 cm/s) repeated three times, but over the randomized body sites also. After each brush stroke, the participant will rate pleasantness and intensity. This will allow us to compare between perception over the sites directly. Tactile detection thresholds will be measured at each site using calibrated monofilaments (Aesthesio set, Ugo Basile).

Fig. 1. Experimental setup. (A) Schema of the rotary tactile stimulator robot. (B) The five skin sites tested, indicated as stars. (C) Installation of the participant.

3 Expected results

We expect an inversely proportional relationship between breast sensibility and breast size, at least for tactile detection thresholds. We also expect to find a lower sensibility

in breast areola-complex than in glabrous skin of the hand, suggesting a lower innervation density. We predict variations across torso skin sites in terms of temperature perception, especially for warm detection [6]. Regarding affective touch, we expect to find a negative quadratic relationship between stroking velocities and pleasantness rating, like at other skin sites [7]. However, we predict differences between skin sites, which may be found in the first and/or the second series of experiments, where torso stroking may be less pleasant [3] and less intense. We also expect to find correlations between our measures, including experimental tests and the supplementary information gathered. The tactile and thermal perception data may relate to the density and type of skin receptors present, including A β mechanoreceptors, C-tactile afferents, and thermoreceptors. Our goal is to better understand these fundamental mechanisms to apply the insights to reproduce realistic sensations in breast prosthetics, after mastectomy [2].

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